

Fungal Diversity and pH Quality Assessment of Commercial Packaged Drinking Water Sold in Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Water is indispensable and plays a pivotal role in all life processes. In spite of its indispensability, access to safe and clean water remains a global challenge, particularly in countries with limited resources such as Nigeria. This study comparatively assessed the fungal diversity of sachet and bottled water sold in Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria. A total of sixteen (16) water samples eight sachet and eight bottled were collected and analyzed for fungal count and pH using standard microbiological techniques. The results revealed moderate fungal loads across sachet and bottled brands with the highest concentrations in sachet brands. Fungal isolates including *Saccharomyces*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Penicillium chrysogenum* were identified based on morphological characterization in both sachet and bottled water exhibiting a higher frequency of contamination. These organisms exhibited variability in distribution across both sachet and bottled water brands. Their prevalence in these packaged water samples implies significant lapses in production hygiene and quality control. The result of the pH analysis shows that most of the sachet water showed slight acidity while a few fall within the acceptable range (6.5-8.5). Similarly, in bottled water, two samples demonstrated acidity, while six samples showed neutrality. This suggest that most sachet water brands in Agbor may pose risk of mild acidity. Based on the outcome of the study, sachet and bottled water sold in Agbor pose a significant threat to public health and calls for strict measures and sanctions by regulatory agencies to ensure compliance with standards, with a view to safeguarding public health.

Keywords: Sachet water, Bottled water, fungal diversity, Public health, waterborne diseases

INTRODUCTION

Water is a renewable natural resource critical for ecosystems, human survival and all life processes (Ming *et al.*, 2025). In spite of its indispensability, access to safe and clean water remains a global challenge. Data on a global scale show that millions of people worldwide, particularly in resource-limited settings are living with waterborne diseases, and that 485,000 deaths are recorded annually (Tetteh Tettey, 2025), highlighting a critical public health challenge. Packaged water (either as sachet, bottled or refill) has become an important element of water security in many low and middle income countries, owing to poor reliability and lack of piped water infrastructure (Vedachalam *et al.*, 2017). The competitive edge of packaged water over piped alternatives-mainly based on perceived availability, affordability and accessibility is questionable as studies have demonstrated the prevalence of pathogenic organisms in packaged drinking water (Dubal *et al.*, 2025). These realities constitute a serious threat to public health.

In Nigeria for example, millions of households depend on packaged (sachet and bottled) water, owing to insufficient municipal water supply and inadequate public utilities (Ijioma *et al.*, 2025). The inadequacy of portable water supply accelerates the proliferation of sachet and bottled water facilities across Nigeria, thereby bridging the gaps in portable water access. Due to its affordability, sachet water- commonly known in Nigeria as pure water holds a competitive edge over bottled water (Onodugo *et al.*, 2025). Sachet and bottled water have improved water supply especially in underserved localities across Nigeria and other parts of Africa (Onodugo *et al.*, 2025). In spite of the affordability and accessibility of packaged water in Nigeria, its microbiological quality falls short. Studies

have isolated different arrays of microorganisms in packaged water sample. For example, studies on packaged water across different West African Countries have continued to demonstrate that these products fail to meet microbiological safety standards (Ami *et al.*, 2025; Jimoh *et al.*, 2025). Fungal species including *Asperigillus*, *penicillium*, and *Saccharomyces* have also been isolated from packaged water, further raising public health concerns (Mohammed and Al-Taie, 2024). Recent study by Jimoh, et al. (2024) have detected the presence of *E. coli*, *salmonella*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* in both sachet and bottled water in Nigeria.

Routes of contamination varies; ranging from pre-production to post-production, storage and distribution of final products (Sehgal, *et al.*, 2024). The water used to produce these sachet and bottled water is sourced from boreholes, which are vulnerable to microbial pollution due to runoff from rainfall and their proximity to pit latrines (Omorogieva *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, some of the production materials such film, preform (polyethylene terephthalate), caps etc., are low in quality and do not meet standards, thereby increasing the susceptibility of packaged drinking water to contaminations. Some factories lack modern technologies to ensure quality water production. For instance most bottled water facilities in Nigeria are not fully automated, thereby creating room for contamination of the final product. As a way of ensuring strict adherence to standard procedures and safeguarding public health, The World Health Organization (WHO), National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) and Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) have sanctioned strict microbiological standards (Ebegba, *et al.*, 2024).

Similar to other parts of Nigeria, the people of Agbor in Delta State, Nigeria depends on sachet and bottled water due to deficiencies in portable water supply (Eyankware and Ephraim, 2021). Over the years, studies have been conducted on the bacteriological and fungal safety of packaged water. However, there is dearth of studies comparing fungal diversity of bottled and sachet water into a single research workflow. This research fills this gap by providing comparative data on the fungal diversity in both sachet and bottled water

sold in Agbor Delta State. By making such data available, this research seeks to draw the attention of the regulatory agencies and policy makers as well as creating consumer awareness with the overall aim of safeguarding public health.

Material and Methods

Study Area

The study area is Agbor town in Ika South Local Government Area, Delta State, Nigeria. Agbor is a semi-urban settlement covering approximately 650 square kilometers, with an estimated population of 162,594 residents (NPC, 2018).

Fig.1: Map of Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria. (Olobaniyi *et al.*, 2007).

Collection of Samples

A total of sixteen (16) water samples were obtained, comprising eight (8) sachet water samples and eight (8) bottled water samples, each from various brands and locations. The collected samples were carefully sealed in sterile polyethylene bags and promptly transported to the laboratory for microbiological examination.

FUNGI PROCEDURE

Formulation of Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA)

A total of 39 grams of potato dextrose agar (PDA) powder was dissolved in one liter of distilled water inside a conical flask, which was then sealed with cotton wool and covered with aluminum foil. The mixture was thoroughly stirred and sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes. After sterilization, the medium was allowed to cool to approximately 50°C before being aseptically poured into Petri dishes within a laminar flow cabinet.

Isolation of Fungi

The prepared agar medium, intended for fungal cultivation, was aseptically dispensed into Petri dishes and incubated at 28°C for 72 hours. Following successful microbial growth, the resulting colonies were enumerated using a colony counter, and the data corresponding to each dilution level was documented.

The concentration of colony-forming units per milliliter (CFU/mL) was then determined using the following formula:

$$\text{CFU/ml} = \frac{\text{number of colonies}}{\text{volume plated} \times \text{dilution factor}}$$

Cultural Characteristics

The physical characteristics of each colony such as size, surface texture, pigmentation, and coloration on the reverse side were assessed through visual inspection..

Pure culture

One single colony was identified and re-streaked as a primary inoculum on the surface of a potato Dextrose agar plate medium to make a pure culture. After achieving a pure culture, the same colony was streaked onto potato dextrose agar slant. These cultures were incubated at 25°C for 72h.

Lactophenol Cotton Blue Mounting

Lactophenol cotton blue is widely used in mycology for preparing semi-permanent slides of fungal samples for microscopic analysis. It stains the cytoplasm of fungal cells while creating a pale blue background that enhances the visibility of hyphal walls. The stain is composed of four main ingredients: phenol, which acts as a fungicide; lactic acid, which helps clear the specimen; cotton blue, which imparts color to the fungal cytoplasm; and glycerin, which helps preserve the preparation. For permanent slide preparations, glycerin can be substituted with polyvinyl alcohol in the mounting solution.

This staining method is suitable for the quick and routine observation of a wide range of fungi. A small portion of fungal material, especially one containing spores or reproductive structures, is placed in a drop of the stain on a clean microscope slide. A cover slip is then gently positioned over the sample, making it ready for immediate microscopic examination.

Procedure

Apply a drop of lactophenol cotton blue stain onto a clean microscope slide.

Using a sterilized, cooled needle, transfer a small portion of fungal material preferably containing spores or spore-bearing structures into the drop. Carefully tease apart the fungal

sample with an inoculating needle to disperse it within the stain. Gently mix the mold structures with the stain.

Finally, place a cover slip over the preparation, ensuring that no air bubbles are trapped beneath.

Observation

Observe the slide preparation using both low and high-power objectives of the microscope. Note and describe the morphological features observed, including the structure and type of hyphae, the form of conidiophores, the appearance of conidia, and how the conidia are arranged along the cells. Sketch the microscopic field as seen under both magnifications, accurately representing the features observed. Use the morphological characteristics to identify the fungal species present. Under the microscope, the fungal cytoplasm appears as a faintly stained blue area lining the interior of the transparent cell walls of hyphae, conidiophores, phialides, and conidia. This entire structure is viewed against a pale blue background provided by the stain on the slide.

Measurement of pH

The pH levels of the samples will be measured using a digital pH meter. For each measurement, the pH electrode will be immersed in the water sample and held in place for a few minutes to allow the reading to stabilize before recording the value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fungal counts from Sachet and bottled Water Samples sold in Agbor Delta State is presented in Table 1. The fungal count ranged from 3.00×10^{-3} - 8.00×10^{-3} . The highest count was found in S4, while S1 recorded the lowest count. In bottled samples, the lowest counts were found in S4 and

S5 ($2.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$), while the highest counts was recorded in S6 ($10.67 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.33$). However, no count was observed in S2, S3 and S8.

Table 1: Mean Fungal Counts from sachet and bottled sample water sold in Agbor Delta State.

Sachet sample ID	Fungi Count (PDA)	Bottle sample ID	Fungi Count (PDA)
S1	$3.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$	B1	$5.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$
S2	$6.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$	B2	—
		B3	—
S3	$7.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$		
S4	$8.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$	B4	$2.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$
S5	$5.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$	B5	$2.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$
S6	$6.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$	B6	$10.67 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.33$

S7	$5.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$	B7	$4.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$
S8	$5.00 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.00$	B8	–

KEY: Results are expressed as Mean \pm SEM. S1-S8 represents different brands of sachet and bottled water sold in Agbor, Delta State.

The cultural characteristics of fungi isolated from sachet and bottled water sold in Agbor, Delta State are presented in Table 2

The fungi identified on the bases of morphology were *Saccharomyces sp.*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Penicillium chrysogenum*.

TABLE 2: The cultural characteristics of fungi isolated from sachet and bottled water sold in Agbor, Delta State

Cultural characteristics/Nature of colony	Morphological characteristics		
	Nature of hyphae	Spore type	Organism
Cream colonies with pale reverse side	Pseudohyphae	Chlamyospore	<i>Saccharomyces sp.</i>
Fluffy colonies with black spores and a pale reverse side	Septate	Conidiospore	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
Fluffy mass with light green spores, yellow areas and a pale reverse side	Septate	Conidiospore	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
Green dome shaped colonies with dirty white reverse colouration	Septate	Conidiospore	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>

Table 3 shows the distribution pattern of fungi isolates from sachet and bottled water sold in Agbor, Delta State. *Saccharomyces sp* occurred in 7 sachet water samples but was detected in one bottled water sample. *Aspergillus niger* was found in 3 sachet water samples, while it was detected in one bottled brand. Similarly, *Penicillium chrysogenum* was detected in 3 sachet water samples and one bottled water sample. However, *Aspergillus flavus* was only detected in one bottled water sample.

TABLE 3: Distribution Pattern of Fungi Isolates

SOURCE	<i>Saccharomyces sp.</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
S1		+		
S2	+			
S3	+	+		
S4	+	+		
S5	+		+	
S6	+		+	
S7	+		+	
S8	+			
B1			+	
B2		+		
B3				
B4		+		
B5	+			
B6				+
B7				

B8

Fig 1. Distribution pattern of fungal isolates in sachet and bottled water samples sold in Agbor, Delta State. From the figure above, *Saccharomyces sp* occurred in 7 sachet water samples but occurred in one bottled water sample. *Aspergillus niger* was found in 3 sachet water samples, while it was detected in one bottled brand. Similarly, *Penicillium chrysogenum* was detected in 3 sachet water samples and one bottled water sample. However, *Aspergillus flavus* was only detected in one bottled water sample.

The results of pH concentrations of sachet and bottled water sold in Agbor Delta State are presented in Table 4. Five (5) sachet water samples show slight acidity (5.79, 5.88, 5.69, 5.38, 6.02), while three (3) sachet water samples demonstrate near neutrality (6.55, 6.39, and 6.51). On the other hand, three (3) bottled water samples show slight acidity (5.52, 5.88, 5.59), four (4) bottled water samples show near neutrality (6.67, 6.60, 6.32, 6.51), and one (1) bottled water sample show neutrality (6.96).

TABLE 4: Comparison of pH concentrations of bottled water and sachet water samples

Water Type	Sample Name	R1	R2	R3	Mean pH
Sachet	S1	5.84	5.77	5.76	5.79
Sachet	S2	6.59	6.53	6.52	6.55
Sachet	S3	5.90	5.82	5.86	5.86
Sachet	S4	5.75	5.66	5.67	5.69
Sachet	S5	5.47	5.36	5.31	5.38
Sachet	S6	6.44	6.36	6.37	6.39
Sachet	S7	6.55	6.49	6.48	6.51
Sachet	S8	6.11	6.00	5.95	6.02

Bottle	B1	5.51	5.53	5.51	5.52
Bottle	B2	7.04	7.02	6.82	6.96
Bottle	B3	6.69	6.68	6.63	6.67
Bottle	B4	5.95	5.84	5.86	5.88
Bottle	B5	6.64	6.55	6.62	6.60
Bottle	B6	6.46	6.29	6.20	6.32
Bottle	B7	5.57	5.63	5.58	5.59
Bottle	B8	6.55	6.49	6.48	6.51

DISCUSSION

Although WHO and NIS do not provide explicit permissible limits for fungi in drinking water, their presence is generally discouraged because certain fungal species can produce mycotoxins and other metabolites that may pose health risks. The prevalence of fungi in packaged water is often attributed to post-treatment contamination, particularly from air, improperly sterilized packaging materials, or storage under unfavorable conditions (Duque-Sarango *et al.*, 2025). The fungal presence in the studied samples, while relatively low, indicates lapses in sterilization or storage conditions.

As shown in Table 2, fungal isolates obtained from water samples in Agbor, Delta State, were characterized based on their cultural and morphological traits, including colony structure, hyphal features, and spore formation. *Saccharomyces* species appeared as cream-

colored colonies with a faint reverse coloration, exhibiting pseudohyphae and producing chlamydo-spores. Tischne et al. (2021) discovered the presence of *saccharomyces sp* in packaged water in a health facility, which is in line with the present study's finding. This yeast-like fungus is generally non-pathogenic but may indicate organic matter presence and post-treatment contamination. *Aspergillus niger* formed fluffy colonies with black spores and a pale reverse, with septate hyphae and conidiospores. *Aspergillus flavus* produced a fluffy mass with light green spores and yellow areas, also with septate hyphae and conidiospores. This aligns with the findings of Innocent et al. (2022), who discovered *Aspergillus flavus* in packaged water samples sold in a southern University, Nigeria. These two *Aspergillus* species are common in the environment and known for their ability to produce mycotoxins (e.g., aflatoxins), which pose serious health risks if ingested over time (Cabral, 2010). *Penicillium chrysogenum* showed green, dome-shaped colonies with a dirty white reverse, septate hyphae, and conidiospores. Although often regarded as a beneficial mold due to its role in penicillin production, its presence in drinking water indicates possible exposure to air or organic-rich surfaces during bottling. The detection of these fungi, especially toxin-producing *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* species, suggests substandard hygienic conditions in water processing and packaging.

Fungal contamination levels varied among sachet and bottled water samples collected from Agbor, Delta State, with four fungal genera identified: *Saccharomyces sp.*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, and *Aspergillus flavus*. *Saccharomyces sp.* was the most commonly detected, appearing in seven of the sachet water samples and one of the bottled water sample. This yeast, though generally non-pathogenic, may indicate high organic content and post-treatment contamination. The presence of *Aspergillus niger* in some of the samples suggests widespread environmental exposure. Its ability to produce spores that are airborne and resist standard water treatments raises concerns, especially as it can be opportunistic in immunocompromised individuals. *Penicillium chrysogenum* was detected in three sachet water samples and one bottled water sample. While this mold is notable for its role in antibiotic production, its presence in drinking water indicates contamination through air, poor sanitation, or

storage conditions (Innocent *et al.*, 2022). This findings are in consonant with the study conducted by Olawale et al. (2025) who detected the occurrence of these organisms in sachet and bottled water. Overall, sachet water samples showed a higher frequency of fungal contamination than bottled water, suggesting relatively poorer hygienic practices or lower production standards. Although WHO and NIS guidelines do not set specific limits for fungi in drinking water, their presence is undesirable and may signal risk for allergic reactions, infections, or mycotoxin exposure, especially in vulnerable populations (WHO, 2017).

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2017) and Nigerian Industrial Standard (NIS 554:2007) specify that the pH of safe drinking water should fall between 6.5 and 8.5 to prevent it from being overly acidic or alkaline, ensuring it remains safe for both human health and plumbing systems. Based on the findings, 6 out of 8 sachet water samples and 4 out of 8 bottled water samples recorded pH levels below 6.5, indicating acidity. The acidic nature of several water samples may result from source water characteristics, inadequate pH adjustment during treatment, or carbon dioxide absorption due to poor sealing. Consuming water with low pH over time may not cause acute health issues but could potentially leach metals like lead or copper from pipes, affect taste, and in sensitive individuals, irritate the gastrointestinal tract (WHO, 2017).

CONCLUSION

Fungal contamination, particularly with toxigenic species such as *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*, was more evident in sachet water compared to bottled water. The presence of these fungi poses potential risks for immunocompromised individuals and emphasizes the need for continuous fungal monitoring in packaged drinking water. The high acidity levels of most of the water samples as against the recommended standards further underscores the public health risks of packaged water. This study therefore serves as a wakeup call for the relevant regulatory agencies to sanction stricter measures and regulations and to raise public awareness with a view to safeguarding public health.

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